

FOSTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE: REPRESENTING LINGUISTIC KNOWLEDGE

Purpose. *This study presents the framework of mastering foreign language grammar within the University curriculum. Fostering learners' grammatical competence (GC) is identified as a current target of grammar acquisition. The premise is advanced that to achieve the goal set the teaching and learning process has to take into account multiple factors, which facilitate enhancing grammatical awareness that conduces to English proficiency.*

Scientific Novelty. *It is surmised that developing GC can be efficacious providing the teacher considers cognitive profiles of students and reckons in affective determinants of learning. In this paper, a special emphasis is placed on multiple modes of introducing grammatical items that may be represented in a number of ways, among which the most common are schemas, models, algorithms, rules, illustrative charts, and conceptual metaphors. The rationale of this premise is grounded on the assertion that reasonably combining various types of linguistic input may turn out beneficial for the understanding, internalization and conceptualization of the subject matter.*

Methodology. *To identify the ways of grammatical conceptualization, several methods were employed, specifically, the scientific method, the qualitative method and the quantitative method, which in combination turned out instrumental in establishing the conditions for grammatical conceptualization in the English language course.*

Conclusion. *Grammatical conceptualization is a gradual process that involves progressing through several knowledge states, which correlate with the phases of learners' language development. The activation of existing concepts in the minds of cognizing subjects may occur yet when they perceive grammatical material; therefore, the stage of introducing linguistic input takes on a more important meaning in the process of English grammar acquisition.*

Key words: *grammar acquisition, grammatical competence, cognitive profiles, types of linguistic information, grammatical conceptualization.*

Introduction. This paper presents the results of a long-lasting research in the field of bilingual Pedagogy, specifically, in the domain of teaching English grammar within the University curriculum. In particular, the study focuses on the factors that promote reasonable ways of representing the subject matter, which can conduce the learners to conceptualize and internalize linguistic knowledge, and subsequently, adequately apply it in their own productive speech when exposed to real-life communicative settings. With this in view, the article evolves around the process of turning explicit linguistic knowledge (knowing-WHAT as with the theoretical understanding of the subject matter) into implicit (knowing-HOW as with practical skills). The idea is justified that this process tends to play an important role in FL acquisition since grammar not only lays the groundwork for effective communication but also develops learners' cognitive and grammatical skills as the main constituents of their grammatical competence (GC).

A number of scholars addressed the issue of developing GC and considered it from various angles. Specifically, A. Hornby (1979) advanced the idea of presenting grammar structures in illustrative situations; S. Krashen (1981) held the view of taking into account an affective filter while acquiring grammatical skills; Ye. Passov (1991) put forward the idea of presenting grammar phenomena one at a time by quanta; G. Kitaigorodskaya (1992) singled out a stage in the model Synthesis₁ – Analysis – Synthesis₂ for analyzing linguistic items; O. Nitsetskaya (1998) promoted a strategy of perceiving grammar material in the form of «heuristic sessions»; L. Chernovatyi (1999) emphasized the importance to employ structured linguistic information for presenting grammar material. Despite multitudinous efforts of scholars to solve the problem of effective FL grammar acquisition and foster GC among University students, it remains at the core of many debated

issues in the areas of bilingual education. Moreover, the continuous interest in manyfaceted grammar matters still raises numerous controversies among academics.

Purpose and Tasks. This paper will first outline in a sketchy fashion an integrated overview of GC as a target of teaching FL grammar, it will then go on to reveal the challenges, which FL trainees may encounter while acquiring GC, and finally, it will expose the reasonable ways of overcoming these challenges employing diverse types of linguistic material. One of the problems that learners may stumble over in a language course is the understanding, conceptualization and internalization of grammar input. This problem tends to stem from the ineffective representation of grammar items. Accordingly, the ways of representing grammar structures with pertinent rationales are a key axis around which this study is formed.

Materials for analysis. Based on the latest research, GC is looked upon as a constituent of linguistic competence; at the same time, GC also encompasses a set of components, namely [3, 112]: (1) a system knowledge of a FL, its grammatical notions, concepts and categories, and means of their expressions; (2) an ability to conceptualize grammar input; (3) skills to utilize grammar items appropriately in terms of registers, standards and usage in order to realize communicative intentions adequately to situations. With regard to foregoing, it is deemed plausible to assert that a high level of GC is conducive to effective communication, since improper grammar can negatively affect the meaning and clarity of an intended message.

Scientific Novelty. Giving pre-eminence to GC as a sought-for target of FL grammar acquisition entrains elaborating theoretical premises on which this process may be grounded. These premises posit the necessity to take into account affective factors in the teaching process, students' individual mental and psychological differences, learning and epistemic styles, dominant hemispheres and sensory channels of perceiving input. Integrated together they make up learners' cognitive profiles upon which preferable ways of presenting and processing linguistic information may be dependent. The aforementioned assumptions require cursory clarification in order to reveal how they manifest themselves in a University FL course.

Pursuant to S. Krashen, linguistic competence may be advanced when language is acquired subconsciously and that the learners' ability to acquire language is constrained if they are experiencing negative emotions such as fear or embarrassment [12, 71]. It implies that the effective acquisition of FL grammar needs reckoning in the factor of an affective filter.

An affective filter is a theoretical construct that attempts to explain the emotional variables associated with the success or failure of acquiring a FL. It is clear therefore that when the affective filter is high, individuals may experience stress, anxiety, and lack of self-confidence that may inhibit successful acquisition of language skills [20]. On this basis, it may be inferred that teachers of FL must strategically organize their learners' environment and instruction in order to lower their affective filter in the classroom. In particular, overemphasis on error correction, mocking at mistakes, being placed in awkward or high-risk environments may tend to increase the affective filter and retard language development. With regard to the aforementioned, it stands to reason to hypothesize that too sophisticated techniques of representing linguistic information may also increase the level of the learners' affective filter, reciprocally, lower their self-confidence and bring about fear that they will be unable to understand the subject matter. In its turn, fear engenders inhibition in the cerebral cortex – that may slow down FL grammar acquisition, result in poor language production and hence, overall speech and cogitative performance of the students.

In relation to the foregoing, yet the founder of Suggestopedia G. Lozanov (1978) indicated that it is out of fear that learners «do not use full mental powers» but set up «psychological barriers» because they are afraid that they will be limited in their ability to perform or that they will fail. The scholar believed therefore that negative thoughts of subjects about their learning ability have to be «de-suggested». Furthermore, G. Lozanov held the view that individuals are capable of learning «at rates many times greater than what we commonly assume to be the limits of human performance». He asserted that most people do not make use of their brain capacity and hence, do not reach the learning ability they would be able to develop otherwise [15, 34–35].

To increase the learners' **brain capacity**, it seems reasonable to engage in the process of FL acquisition both hemispheres. Though they perform different functions (specifically, the right side of the brain is more artistic and creative whereas the left side is more academic and logical), they are mutually related due to the corpus callosum, which allows the two hemispheres to communicate with each other by transmitting messages back and forth between them [11]. The indications are therefore that their interplay in the learning process may appear advantageous for cognition in a language course. That is why the intent of fostering the two hemispheres to operate in tandem seems relevant, since mastering a FL can be significantly improved when both sides of the brain are involved in it.

With reference to the mentioned above, it is pertinent to bring to the forefront of this study the idea of embracing **multimodal learning**, which may significantly facilitate the perception and understanding of grammar material under study. Multimodal learning environments allow grammar items to be presented in more than one sensory mode – visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. Multimedia enhancements in these environments include video and audio elements, images, recorded presentations, interactive audio-enhanced diagrams, simulations, and graphics to cater more efficaciously to various learning styles of the students. Thus, multimedia can be employed to represent the content knowledge in the ways that mesh with learning styles of the subjects, which in turn, may

appeal to their modal preferences [16, 311]. It would be appropriate to assume that, on the one hand, learning styles are determined by dominant sensory channels of the students, and, on the other hand, learning styles themselves determine harmonious learning strategies, chosen by the teacher in appliance with individual differences of the learners.

According to P. Shah and E. Freedman (2003), a number of benefits may emerge when using visualizations in learning environments, specifically [19, 317]: (1) promoting learning by providing an external representation of information; (2) a deeper processing of information; (3) maintaining the students' attention by making information more engaging and motivating. The major benefit of those, as identified by A. Picciano (2009), is that it «allows students to experience learning in ways in which they are most comfortable, while challenging them to experience and learn in other ways as well» [17, 13]. Consequently, the advantages of multimodal learning are crucial to making complex informational stimuli easier to comprehend, conceptualize, internalize and retain.

Given this evidence, it can be inferred that employing their individual mental resources, dominant hemispheres and sensory channels of perceiving input the learners may develop certain strategies of performing communicative and cognitive activity in the course of knowing, which conform to their cognitive profiles. Inter alia, those strategies become apparent in corresponding *epistemic styles* (i.e. ways of knowing) of the cognizing subjects – empirical (based on practical experience), rationalist (based on logical inferences and represented by conceptual schemes, models, categories, etc.), and metaphorical (based on a diversity of impressions and a combination of knowledge, personalized perception of reality and intuition). Via epistemic styles, the learners perceive the world, process information and acquire knowledge [8, 137]. The idea of epistemic styles was introduced by J. Royce, who sees rationalism, empiricism, and metaphorism as higher order personality integrators, which are the primary determinants of individual differences in worldview. More specifically, variations in epistemic style hierarchies and their corresponding cognitive profiles reflect variations in cognitive (i.e. both abilities and styles) strengths and weaknesses [18, 152].

Commonly, cognition is done through thought, experience, and the senses, respectively, the ways of cognition are mirrored in the consentaneous styles, which reveal themselves in various approaches to mastering a FL that the students choose to take. Epistemic styles may also be reflected in the manner of processing linguistic information that an instructor prefers to utilize in the classroom in order to visualize the subject matter (e.g., charts, schemas, algorithms, models, metaphors, etc.). These types of linguistic information tend to conform to the learners' epistemic styles. Reciprocally, they may turn out beneficial for each particular student while absorbing and assimilating linguistic knowledge.

Extending the aforementioned, epistemic styles can affect the learners' mental representations, which are regarded both as a fixed form of structured knowledge and a procedure implying cognitive activity for processing information [8, 98]. The indications are therefore that mental representations are concepts, entities that exist in the mind; their creation is the result of human activity; they depend on a new situation and on the activation of already existing concepts of acquired knowledge under definite conditions for specific purposes. Furthermore, concepts are basic units («quanta») of mental resources, building blocks of thoughts that make up a conceptual system of an individual [14].

Methodology. To identify the ways of grammatical conceptualization, several methods were employed for this study. Specifically, it was essential to use the scientific method aimed at revealing possible modes of representing grammar items (it also incorporated observation and numerous experimentation to verify the formulated hypothesis). The qualitative method was targeted at determining the students' learning and epistemic styles, dominant hemispheres and types of intelligence (these were described subjectively). The quantitative method was utilized for processing the data and generating a new hypothesis based on the results of the obtained evidence. In combination, the employed methods appeared instrumental in establishing the conditions for grammatical conceptualization of the cognizing subjects in the English language course.

It is worthwhile at this stage to specify what concepts can be formed or activated in the minds of the students in a language course. N. Boldyrev (2001) holds the view that the most fundamental concepts are encoded in a language and become apparent in grammar. He emphasizes the idea that the most important part of conceptual information of different levels of complexity and abstraction is fixed in the overall structure of a language in the form of grammatical concepts, which are reflected in grammatical forms, categories, and syntactical structures. Furthermore, the scholar groups grammatical concepts into three types: 1) elementary or one-dimensional; 2) bi-dimensional; 3) multi-dimensional [2, 43]. They crave a brief explication.

Elementary grammatical concepts do not cause ambiguity, for instance, in the English language they may be represented by verbs in the 3^d person singular in the Present Simple tense, e.g.: *writes, goes, plays, has, simplifies*); adverbs, derived from adjectives, e.g.: *quickly, fluently, correctly*); plural nouns, e.g.: *tomatoes, armies, glasses, knives, children, women*.

In contrast, bi-dimensional concepts are more complex in nature and have a more complex cognitive rationale, for instance, grammatical number, which may fall into this category due to its cognitive basis that encompasses the notion of quantity and ways of its realization in language. More specifically, the use of grammar forms expressing number depends on such characteristics as countability – uncountability, discontinuity – continuity, collectiveness – non-collectiveness, etc. Commonly, in the English language plural nouns are formed

with the help of the suffix *-(e)s*. However, there are unconventional ways to form plural nouns via [5, 41]: (1) the archaic suffix *-en* (*ox – oxen*); (2) the change of a root vowel (*tooth – teeth, goose – geese*); (3) the suffixes in the words of Greek and Latin origin (*corpus – corpora, symposium – symposia, phenomenon – phenomena, alumnus – alumni, thesis – theses*); (4) a formal concurrence of forms in the singular and in the plural (*sheep – sheep, deer – deer, buffalo – buffalo, fish – fish, fruit – fruit*). The latter case may cause ambiguity as the nouns *fish* and *fruit* can form a plural dually, e.g.: *fish* and *fishes, fruit* and *fruits*, which differ in meanings. Particularly, the plural form that has a marker signals about something of different kinds, e.g. [5, 113]: *Several fishes in the region have become extinct. You should eat three different fruits per day*. The plural form that has no marker means a certain quantity of some objects or species, e.g.: *There is not much fresh fruit available at this time of the year. There are five fish in the aquarium*.

The third group – multi-dimensional grammatical concepts – are even more complex in nature and are determined by pragmatics of communication. This group of concepts may be represented by the category of grammatical tense, which inter alia encompasses the notion of deictic perspective, that is the idea of real and grammatical time (the present, the past and the future), and the notion of the moment of speaking, which establishes correlation between real and grammatical time, e.g.: *«The insurance inspector came. He said that they have evidence»* (F. Scott Fitzgerald, *The Great Gatsby*). In the provided example, the Sequence of Tenses is not observed for various reasons: first, the information correlates not only with a past moment but also with a moment of speaking; second, the speaker emphasizes the importance of the delivered information. In the next instance, *Harry said that his wife is ill* the Sequence of Tenses is not observed because the information is significant for the speaker. In this case, the grammatical concept is motivated by pragmatics of communication.

The category of grammatical aspect, which expresses how an action, event, or state, denoted by a verb, extends over time, may also be assigned to the group of multi-dimensional concepts. This category is also complex in nature: on the one hand, it shows whether the aspect of an action is perfective or imperfective, and on the other hand, it demonstrates whether an action is finite or non-finite [2, 44.]. For example: 1. *By the time the commandos had smashed through the entrance, the terrorist leader had barricaded himself in the bedroom* (E. Segal, *The Class*). In this instance in the subordinate clause, the verb *to smash* is used in the Past Perfect tense to underscore the fact of lost time. 2. *By the time he had reached the allegro of the third movement, he was too involved to be diffident* (E. Segal, *The Class*). In this example in the subordinate clause, the verb *to reach* is used in the Past Perfect tense to pinpoint the importance of the situation. It is believed that the intentional violation of a grammatical rule attracts the reader's attention and facilitates understanding of the psychological state of a character. This given, it may be inferred that multi-dimensional grammatical concepts imply interpreting extra-linguistic information via definite notions, which constitute the cognitive basis of grammatical concepts.

Overall, the data seem to be strong to indicate that grammatical conceptualization is a gradual process, which involves progressing through various knowledge states, which correlate with the phases of language development of an individual. These knowledge states entail complexifying and activating grammatical concepts in the process of cognition.

Results. It would be appropriate to assume that the activation of existing concepts in the mind of students may occur when they perceive grammar material. It may be presented in a number of ways. In FL pedagogy, the ways of presenting grammar items are defined as *linguistic information*. In fact, it is a sort of linguistic stimuli, which reduce the degree of uncertainty of the learners in the actual situation and, accordingly, in their subsequent verbal behavior. Linguistic information may be conveyed by various means; their choice depends on how adequately they reveal and impart knowledge about the subject matter [9, 33]. This paper aims to illuminate and illustrate the most prominent types of linguistic information, which may significantly facilitate FL grammar acquisition.

A SPEECH PATTERN – a typical speech unit, which serves as a basis for making analogous speech units with the same design [1, 298]. It is maintained that a speech pattern automatically launches the mechanism of analogy enhancing the learners to construct similar meaningful units. This can be accounted for by the fact that a speech pattern implicitly contains a precept for constructing a phrase or sentence with the identical framework. For instance, the teacher sets a communicative task to the students: *Inform your peer what New Year resolutions your group-mates made. Follow the given pattern: X promised that he/she would start / stop ... doing smth.* The students construct their own sentences in accordance with the given pattern:

Student₁: Ann promised that she would start jogging.

Student₂: Peter promised that he would quit smoking.

Student₃: Val promised that she would fall to attending Japanese classes.

MODEL – a representation of a studied grammar structure in terms of a drawing or a sign formula, which reproduces the properties and relations between the elements of a modeled structure, thereby facilitating the process of obtaining knowledge about it [1, 159]. Such a model is easy to understand; it provides instantaneous perception of the grammar structure, and it does not require special efforts to memorize it. In addition, a model is dynamic, i.e. it can perform structural transformations that lead to a change in the meaning of a sentence, for

example, making it interrogative or negative. The first instance of the model will be symbolized in terms of a drawing (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. The graphic model of Passive Voice in the English language

Symbol 1 in the provided model denotes the first component of the passive structure (the Subject), symbol 2 indicates the second component (the Predicate comprising two parts – the auxiliary verb *to be* and participle II of the main verb), symbol 3 designates the third component (its being in parentheses signifies its optional character).

The second instance of the model will be visualized in terms of a sign formula (Fig. 2):

Figure 2. The sign model of the Sequence of Tenses in the English language

The model signifies that the Past tense used in the predicate of the principal clause of a complex sentence determines the Past tense of the predicate in the subordinate clause. The choice of tenses in the subordinate clause is governed by simultaneousness, priority or posteriority of its action with/to the action in the principal clause.

SCHEME – a conventional graphic depiction of a grammar phenomenon [1, 64]. Normally, a scheme falls into two groups: linguistic or static and speech or dynamic. When a scheme represents a grammar item as a phenomenon, it is regarded as linguistic and static; when the object of schematization is a grammatical action, a scheme is viewed as speech and dynamic. The instance below illustrates a linguistic scheme (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. A linguistic scheme of the Sequence of Tenses in the English language

It is believed that a rational combination of dynamic and static schemes may appear efficacious in FL grammar acquisition. For instance (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. A scheme of the Past Perfect tense in the English language

RULE – information about a studied grammar structure and a set of explicit regulations governing a procedure of operating with this structure [1, 233]. Typically, FL Pedagogy distinguishes between descriptive rules and rules-precepts. In particular, descriptive rules are theoretical information about a studied grammar phenomenon whereas rules-precepts are instructions or recommendations that explicitly indicate what actions should be performed to achieve a specific goal; they may be considered direct guidance to action, which takes into account the nature of a grammar structure under study. Typically, rules-precepts have a dynamic character. For instance: *to convey the past action preceding another past action expressed by the predicate of the principal clause use the Past Perfect tense, e.g.: I **didn't know** she **had gone** away.*

ALGORITHM – a sequence of operations to be followed in problem solving, which necessarily ensures its correct solution [9, 167]. In appliance with the objectives of the learning process, algorithms fall into receptive and productive types. A receptive algorithm is a set of instructions that determine an order of identification of a minimum of attributes sufficient for recognizing a particular grammar structure. In contrast, a productive algorithm is a set of precepts targeted at solving a problem of transition from information to be transmitted to linguistic phenomena that can transmit it. Such algorithms contain precepts that determine the order of operations necessary to perform a specific grammatical action [4, 78], e.g. [10, 125]: 1) use **should have + a past participle** when it is too bad that something did not happen; 2) use **shouldn't have + a past participle** when it is too bad that something happened. The instance below (Fig. 5) demonstrates a sequence of operations, which ensure a correct performance of a speech action [4, 79].

Figure 5. An algorithm of the Sequence of Tenses in the English language

ILLUSTRATIVE CHART – a visual aid that colligates grammar phenomena [1, 350]. Commonly, a chart is reckoned both as an indicative basis of an action, and as systematization of previously acquired knowledge, which allows tracing the link between all elements of the grammar items under study that lead to bringing segmental information into a system. Realizing the main functions of visual aids (such as cognitive, generalizing, instructional, controlling and compensatory) illustrative charts induce the students' attention, and foster better comprehension and assimilation of linguistic material. Usually, illustrative charts are classified as linguistic or static and speech or dynamic. Below there is an instance of a static chart (Table 1).

Table 1

		Present	Past	Future
Simple	active	writes	wrote	will write
	passive	is written	was written	will be written
Progressive	active	is writing	was writing	will be writing
	passive	is being written	was being written	–
Perfect	active	have written	had written	will have written
	passive	have been written	had been written	will have been written
Perfect	active	have been writing	had been writing	will have been writing
Progressive	passive	–	–	–

CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR – in an extended sense, it is a mental operation, a strategy of processing information in the mind, a form of conceptualization, a cognitive process, which expresses and forms new concepts, without which it would be impossible to obtain new knowledge. A conceptual metaphor refers to understanding one idea in terms of another; hence, it corresponds to the ability of an individual to capture a similarity between objects. Among numerous functions of a conceptual metaphor, a cognitive and a communicative function are prioritized for several reasons: (1) to enhance the formation of concepts and their clarification in the mind (a cognitive function); (2) to ensure the actualization of existing concepts and their rhematization in the mental and speech process (a communicative function) [6, 4; 7, 15].

The disposed information allows presuming that a conceptual metaphor itself does not create concepts of a particular type, but by analogy, it forms, clarifies and expresses one concept via another. Moreover, it helps a concept to emerge in the mind and to be designated in speech. Respectively, conceptual information of a metaphor can be symbolized verbally and graphically, in terms of drawings, schemes, frames, etc. The instance below illustrates a conceptual metaphor, which is visualized verbally [13, 4–5]: *Irregular verbs are creative. They design their own fancy clothes. They never wear those dull uniforms! Irregular verbs are true artists! Presumably, the learners may conceptualize this metaphor in the following way: Verbs can be looked upon as persons. Their affixes are articles of clothing. Regular forms are uniforms. Irregularity is rebelliousness. Irregularity is creativity.*

The example bellow symbolizes a conceptual metaphor in graphic terms [4, 89] (Fig. 6):

Figure 6. A conceptual metaphor of the Sequence of Tenses in the English language

The illustrated conceptual metaphor of the «Grammar House» allows making the following inferences and generalizations: *The Sequence of Tenses in the English language is employed in complex sentences, which comprise the main and the subordinate clause. Grammatical tenses constitute an interdependent hierarchy with four 'floors', which implies that each 'floor' is subordinated to the antecedent and the succedent 'floor'. Grammatical tenses fall into two basic groups: the Present / Future tenses and the Past tenses. The Present /*

Future tenses (in the principal clause) can ascend all four «floors» of the «house», that is, they harmonize with all tenses (in the subordinate clause). In contrast, the Past tenses (in the principal clause) can ascend only two «floors» of the «house», that is, they only harmonize with the Past and Future-in-the-Past tenses (in the subordinate clause), and cannot be harmony with the Present / Future tenses.

Conclusion. Considering the foregoing, it is plausible to posit that University students can benefit from the integration of all types of linguistic information in the process of FL grammar presentation, which will appear conducive to a deeper understanding of the studied subject matter, acquiring new knowledge, and forming grammatical concepts.

On balance, the rational organization of linguistic information in a FL course requires taking into account individual differences of students, their mental resources and representational capacities, epistemic and learning styles, dominant sensory channels and hemispheres, which will have a positive impact on the understanding and assimilation of grammatical phenomena under study, and consequently, will enhance learners' GC.

Further implications. This article contributes to the understanding of how a process of FL grammar acquisition within a University curriculum may be organized. It also offers several insights into the types of effective representation of grammar items. It is far from being conclusive and provides implications for further research into the ways of developing GC.

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ФОРМУВАННЯ ІНШОМОВНОЇ ГРАМАТИЧНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНЦІЇ: ПРЕДСТАВЛЕННЯ МОВНИХ ЗНАНЬ

***Мета статті** – представити концептуальну основу навчання англійської граматики студентів-філологів. Оскільки кінцевою метою навчання визначено формування іношомовної граматичної компетенції, для її досягнення у навчальному процесі слід зважати на низку чинників, що сприяють усвідомленню граматичного матеріалу. Це, своєю чергою, спрощує досягнення високого рівня володіння іноземною мовою.*

***Наукова новизна.** Передбачається, що розвиток граматичної компетенції студентів буде ефективним, за умов врахування викладачем афективних і когнітивних детермінантів суб'єктів пізнання, як-от: індивідуальних психічних особливостей, ментальних здатностей, навчальних стратегій, рівня афективного фільтру, навчальних та епістемологічних стилів, сенсорних каналів сприйняття інформації, способів опрацювання інформації. Сукупно, ці чинники сприятимуть реалізації мультимодального навчання. Особливу увагу надано різним режимам уведення іношомовного граматичного матеріалу, який може бути представлений різними способами, наприклад, за допомогою схем, моделей, алгоритмів, правил, ілюстративних таблиць та концептуальних метафор. Урізноманітнення способів і режимів представлення навчальної інформації сприятиме глибшому розумінню, концептуалізації та засвоєнню матеріалу, що вивчається.*

***Методологія.** Для визначення способів концептуалізації було застосовано декілька методів, зокрема, науковий, квалітативний та квантитативний методи, котрі сукупно виявились визначальними у створенні умов граматичної концептуалізації в процесі оволодіння англійською мовою.*

***Висновки.** Своєю чергою, цей процес сприяє формуванню граматичних концептів у свідомості студентів у процесі оволодіння іноземною мовою. Найважливіші концепти заковдані в мові, більше того, вони проявляються в її граматиці. Граматична концептуалізація є поступовим процесом, який передбачає проходження декількох знаннєвих станів, які корелюють з фазами мовного розвитку суб'єктів навчального процесу. Активація наявних концептів у свідомості студентів відбувається ще на етапі сприйняття граматичного матеріалу, тому етап уведення мовної інформації набуває нового значення в процесі оволодіння граматиною.*

***Ключові слова:** оволодіння граматиною, граматична компетенція, когнітивний профіль, типи лінгвістичної інформації, граматична концептуалізація.*

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